

POLITICS OF THE HOOD: AN ANALYSIS OF HIP-HOP LYRICISM

by

Marianna Rios

ORCID ID: 0009-0008-2507-0730

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11522501

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton

May 2024

Approved by:

Natasha Popowich, M.A., African American Studies

Date:

May 17, 2024

5/24/2024

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

On February 2nd, 2023, I attended a YG concert at the Kia Forum in Inglewood as a part of his “Red Cup Tour.” During this show, YG discussed his controversial song “F*** Donald Trump” and how it stirred the pot between the government and his team. This song’s highly political context and lyrics resulted in a letter sent by the Secret Service to YG. The fact that YG was almost censored surprised me. It also made me wonder, “How could a song be so powerful that the government would view it as such a threat, to the point where they would send the artist a letter about it, almost as if they were attempting to prevent songs of this nature from being created again?” This led me to the era of the *War on Drugs*, as it was the time when hip-hop was born, and the lyrics held the most weight regarding social justice and inequality.

As hip-hop was created in the neighborhoods of New York, many artists gravitated towards it, especially as it transformed from party music into a safe space for their daily experiences to be discussed as young members of the Black community at the time, despite the popular thought of hip-hop being filled with unnecessary violence. In the late 1980s-90s, we saw the idea of the War on Drugs manifest, hitting the streets of the U.S. and beginning to affect neighborhoods of Black families heavily. This is simultaneously occurring while hip-hop is rising and starting to take off. However, the Black community was not only being impacted by the War on Drugs, but around this time, the United States would also create new federal laws that would target them specifically. Hip-hop music itself became a form of protesting and a way of fighting against the oppression they were going through. Now, those songs can be seen as proof of the social and emotional impact that the oppression backed by the U.S. would cause.

Therefore, I will analyze written work that other scholars have done to gain a deeper understanding of the oppression that directly targeted and affected the Black community as early rap came to the scene. I will also analyze specific songs of this timeframe to see first-hand how

these artists were using their voices and this outlet as a way to cry for help and process the structural racism that is constantly working towards the downfall of Black Americans. This paper aims to demonstrate how the 80s-90s hip-hop artists created lyrics that directly reflected their realities and frustrations with structural racism—resulting in what some may consider vulgar or violent-inducing lyrics.

Within hip-hop hits of the '80s and '90s and the scholarship centered around this era, three common themes emerge as a direct outcome of oppression towards the Black community. The first is Mass Incarceration and the “War on Drugs.” Since the colonial era, the U.S. has relied on the oppression and exploitation of people of color to maintain a high class of whites. According to Michelle Alexander in *The New Jim Crow: Mass Incarceration in the Age of Colorblindness*, slavery was the original form of oppression against people of color before the existence of the U.S. Constitution. Even during the creation of the Constitution, there was debate on whether or not the language within the Constitution should include anything regarding the disposal of the slavery system. In the end, it was decided to write the Constitution color-blindly, as it was created to preserve a racial caste system. As explained by Black Studies scholar Cedric Robinson, racial capitalism is the idea that financial gain and racial exploitation go hand in hand in the United States (Kelley, 2017). Therefore, the Constitution is a product and proof of the prominent existence of racial capitalism within the United States. It essentially keeps the nation running as we know it. After all, Alexander also argues that the Thirteenth Amendment did not entirely abolish slavery but instead legalized it as a form of punishment for crimes. The amendment states, “Neither slavery nor involuntary servitude, except as a punishment for crime where of the party shall have been duly convicted, shall exist within the United States, or any place subject to their jurisdiction.” Thus making slavery illegal unless as a form of punishment,

in other words, what we know today as imprisonment. It ultimately made people of color targets. Targeting people of color was further extended with the creation of COINTELPRO, or the Counter Intelligence Program, in 1956, as it made it possible for the government to target civil rights activists (Alexander, 2010). The documentary, *The FBI's War on Black America*, stated that COINTELPRO had targeted Black leaders with four main goals: 1. Prevent the coalition of militant Black nationalist groups, 2. Prevent the rise of a messiah who could unify and electrify the militant Black nationalist movement; 3. Prevent militant Black nationalist groups and leaders from gaining respectability by discrediting them to the community; 4. A final goal should be to prevent the long-range growth of militant Black nationalist organizations, especially among the youth.” Therefore, COINTELPRO was created to prevent Black social justice groups and leaders from being successful in their movements, as they feared a possible rebellion, which ultimately resulted in not only the deaths of many leaders but the incarceration of many also.

In addition to mass incarceration, there was the “War on Drugs,” the government's way of combating illegal drug use and trade within the U.S. by increasing penalties and incarceration terms as well as law enforcement presence among neighborhoods to carry these out. In the article “Unfair by Design: The War on Drugs, Race, and the Legitimacy of the Criminal Justice System,” Lawrence Bobo and Victor Thompson (2006) argue that the War on Drugs also had a profound effect on the Black community because law enforcement officers were encouraged to make arrests in their neighborhoods in an attempt to show progress being made. If that is not enough, attempting to reenter society is even more difficult following their release from prison. Having a criminal record diminishes your chance at employment in the blink of an eye, making it more common for young men of color to be arrested than to obtain a bachelor’s degree, resulting in the continuous cycle of imprisonment and release due to the selling of narcotics being one of

the few jobs readily available after their release. A convicted felon is also exempt from voting privileges in presidential campaigns, making it clear that the legal system was created to “presume, protect, and defend the ideal of the superiority of whites and the inferiority of Blacks” (Bobo & Thompson, 2006).

The “War on Drugs” itself was another direct form of oppression towards people of color. It is what made the mass incarceration system that Alexander discusses able to run in the fashion that it does. Considering the drastic drop in unemployment rates during the Reagan era, many did what was necessary to make ends meet. With the criminalization of marijuana, by the year 2000, 1.1 million people were added to the prisons, and over half of them were labeled drug offenders (Boho & Thompson, 2006).

Due to the oppression they faced from outsiders, many of the Black youth at this time took matters into their own hands and formed street gangs. Gangs were a way of creating a community for self-defense and a sense of power (Chang, 2005). Therefore, the second most common theme within hip-hop of this era is Uniting Against Oppression. According to Jeff Chang in *Can't Stop Won't Stop: A History of the Hip-Hop Generation*, Afrika Bambaataa created “Zulu Nation” to fight for the lives of Black people and fashion a new family for those growing up without one in the Bronx. Afrika Bambaatta quickly grew a reputation amongst the gangs of the Bronx and early hip hoppers, so his influence was immense. Following the Zulu Nation, a new era of gangs would push junkies to get off the streets and would push for peace rather than violence, as reframing street gangs into more positive organizations was their goal (Chang, 2005). Within the Zulu Nation, Bambaata began his invention of hip-hop (Chang, 2005). Hip-hop and rap music provided a space for members of less fortunate communities to express their emotions and speak up for their rights. Imani Perry, in *Profits of the Hood: Politics and*

Poetics in Hip-Hop, argues that hip-hop is an art form, as “provid[ing] not an evaluation of blame but a sophisticated interpretive framework from which to consider racism on both socioeconomic and ideological levels” (Perry, 2004). This resulted in what we know today as early hip-hop and “gangsta rap.”

At the same time, The Black Panther Party had a prominent presence in New York, especially in the Bronx. The Black Panthers were a social justice group that fought for the civil rights of Blacks, all while ensuring a safe environment for the youth of their neighborhoods. However, they did not fear using violence whenever they were met with it by law enforcement or other citizens. After the Party joined with the Chicago Youth Movement, the United States declared war on the Panthers as they were “the greatest threat to internal security” (Chang, 2005). As I previously mentioned, the fall of the Panthers was a result of COINTELPRO incarcerating many Panthers, including their leaders, like Fred Hampton, who was eventually murdered by the FBI (Bennett, 2010).

In *Black Noise: Rap Music and Black Culture in Contemporary America*, Tricia Rose describes rap as “a Black cultural expression that prioritizes Black voices from the margins of urban America” (Rose, 1994). She believes that rap takes on the identity of the narrator, who often speaks from the perspective of a young man longing for social status, touching on how to deal with the loss of a friend and avoid gang violence. Rose argues that rap music and hip-hop are the most significant forms of Black cultural expression that capture the experiences of urban Blacks in America and the ideologies that promote equal opportunity for all (Rose, 1994). Imani Perry similarly argues that the racial discrimination the Black community faced in the '80s and '90s resulted in the creation of hip hop as it became an outlet for them to speak up for their people without needing to fear law enforcement (Perry, 2004).

Gathering in unity has represented power within communities for decades, whether through protests, rallies, or even making records. Afrika Bambaataa proved that music and creating it for a certain group could be powerful, and he paved the way for many hip-hop artists who would come after him.

The collective oppression of the Black community can result in a prejudiced mindset bleeding into society. In *Bodies out of Place: Theorizing Anti-Blackness in U.S. Society*, Barbara Combs states this results in “Black bodies” being viewed as “out of place” amongst white spaces and causes them to face oppression in all aspects of life. This is due to the savior complex many whites may have when it comes to people of color, often believing that they need guidance, mainly because they believe they do not have the mental capacity for certain things (Combs, 2022), which can affect members of the Black community socially and emotionally immensely. This leads me to the third and final most common theme in hip-hop of this era: Oppression’s social and emotional impact.

Oppression results in a profound effect on those who experience it that can cause a variance of responses from joining street gangs to influencing a life after prison. Oppression can even impact innocent Black people trying to purchase homes. Much like Combs emphasizes the impact of oppression, Imani Perry also highlights how the “gangster” persona or “gangsterism” is composed of violence, drug dealing, poverty, desperation, and a lack of education/opportunity, symptoms of oppression. People of poor communities resort to creating their own families (gangs) to make up for the lack of real family they have at home, as well as the lack of support they receive from them and society. It significantly impacts these individuals as it quickly becomes a lifestyle based on loyalty.

According to Bobo and Thompson, prison is seen as the ultimate “end goal” for Blacks in government officials’s eyes, as even the process following their release of reconditioning to societal standards is rarely accomplished. As previously mentioned, their criminal records typically ruin the opportunity for them to be employed and return to a working job, resulting in African Americans having a higher chance of being arrested than obtaining a bachelor's degree. For convicted felons, it is even more challenging as they lose their right to vote during their prison time, and in some cases, they may lose it permanently (Bobo & Thompson, 2006). Ultimately, it has a social and even emotional impact on these individuals, considering it can affect their lives for years, which may lead to mental health concerns like depression and anxiety.

This oppression also bleeds into systems like the housing and criminal justice systems, socially impacting the Black community. Poor Black mothers are targets and viewed as the best candidates for home buying. In *Race for Profit: How Banks and the Real Estate Industry Undermined Black Homeownership*, Keeanga-Yamahtta Taylor states this is because they will likely be unable to keep up with their payments, resulting in foreclosure, where the property could return to the market and be repurchased by their next victims. The family would then be forced back to their lives within poor neighborhoods. Taylor also discusses that when a single Black mother wanted to rent a house, she was given a “better” option to purchase. As the house runs into issues, the woman ultimately spends more money repairing it than she would have if she rented the space she originally wanted, leaving her with no money. The house is then foreclosed and returned to the market, awaiting repurchase (Taylor, 2019).

Hip-hop remains an artifact exemplifying the oppression the Black community faced, both socially and emotionally. Rose argues, “Rap music is, in many ways, a hidden transcript. Among other things, it uses cloaked speech and disguised cultural codes to comment on and

challenge aspects of current power inequalities” (Rose, 1994). Therefore, Hip-hop became a way to restore agency to the Black community, giving us the genre we know and have grown to love today.

As the Black community faced significant discriminatory behavior from others, Hip-Hop became an outlet that was safe for members of the community to bring awareness to the experiences they were facing daily. This can be easily identified from the language used in nearly all 1980s-90s hip-hop songs, which ultimately led to the genre of hip-hop being greatly misconstrued for encouraging violence, retaliation against authority, and the usage of alcohol and drugs. Nonetheless, as Michelle Alexander studied, people of color have been discriminated against since the 1870s and, to this day, are still experiencing high levels of discrimination stemming from racism. Alexander’s study proves that the prejudice they endured since childhood may have contributed to the evolution of hip-hop, which we now know today as early hip-hop music. Not to mention the concept of “Black bodies.” Barbara Combs presents the idea of Black bodies being viewed as “out of place” simply because of the color of their skin (Combs, 2022). This mindset bleeds into those of the public and is supported by the phenomenon of Structural racism. Structural racism is described as the “totality of ways in which societies foster racial discrimination through mutually reinforcing systems of housing, education, employment, earnings, benefits credit, media, health care, and criminal justice” (Bailey et al., 2017).

Structural racism is especially apparent in our criminal justice system. Even as children, Black people are racially discriminated against within the criminal justice system. According to the United Negro College Fund, Black students are 3.8 times more likely to be punished by way of “out-of-school suspensions” once or more and even 2.3 times more likely to be referred to law enforcement or arrested on school-related issues. Authoritative figures targeting these children is

especially harmful as they are most impressionable between the ages of 8 and 10, so this can lead to self-doubt and an embrace of harmful stereotypes (Foulkes et al., 2018). As they grow older, this narrative only worsens. Studies show that between the years 1977-2004, as adults, Black people were more likely to be arrested in comparison to whites (Hinto et al., 2018). The likelihood that Black people will experience the use of force by a police officer is also higher. Structural racism also affects the sentences they received following their arrests, as Black people are more likely to be given more critical sentences than whites as well, which could be life-changing for them.

Police brutality and the obvious existence of structural racism within the U.S. criminal justice system did not become “known” by the public until 1991. In March of 1991, the Los Angeles Police Department brutally beat a Black man, Rodney King, after he led them on a high-speed chase. King was unarmed and had a blood alcohol level that was under the legal limit, yet he suffered severe skull fractures, broken teeth, and permanent brain damage. Eyewitness George Holiday filmed the incident and sent it to a local news station, drawing major attention to the injustice in the video. Unfortunately, King was not the only tragic incident to occur within the Black community (Krbechek & Bates, 2017). Less than two weeks later, 15-year-old Latasha Harlins walked into a corner store to purchase a bottle of orange juice. However, after being accused of stealing, the store owner shoots Harlins in the back of the head even despite her having money in her hand. During the trial for this case, the jury recommended 16 years in prison for involuntary manslaughter. The judge, however, denied this recommendation and gave the offender only five years on probation, a fine of \$500, and 400 hours of community service (Kashanie, 2022). As for the four officers responsible for the beating of King, a verdict was reached a year later, on April 19, 1992, and all officers were acquitted

(Krbechek & Bates, 2017). The outcome of the Rodney King and Latasha Harlins trials sparked the 1992 Los Angeles Riots, as the Black community became enraged with the lack of justice within our social justice system. However, our criminal justice system is not the only institution to suffer from injustice caused by structural racism.

Interestingly enough, our housing system is infected by it as well. In the 1930s, in an attempt to repair the housing shortages caused by the Great Depression, Roosevelt implemented the Public Works Administration, which provided racially segregated housing for Blacks and whites but ultimately benefited whites by increasing their wages. The original mission of Public Housing was to provide housing for the civilian workforce and families of the lower middle class. However, in the 1940s and 1950s, this ultimately left Black families out of the picture as racial covenants were in place that banned members of the Black community from integrated neighborhoods and ultimately confined them to the very overpopulated “ghettos,” which was exacerbated by the practice of redlining (Letiecq et al.,2023). By the 1970s, there was a minimal number of whites living in “ghettos” due to government programs and policies, as well as what is known as “Suburban white flight.” As the government removed all political power and wealth from poor neighborhoods, white people also moved out of these areas as quickly as they could. They moved into suburban areas to remove themselves from the Black community, and in turn, these “ghettos” were created. These separated areas were made possible by “redlining,” defined by Cornell Law School as “the systematic denial of services such as mortgages, insurance loans, and other financial services to residents of certain areas, based on their race or ethnicity.” This further ensures that Black community members will remain confined to these neighborhoods. Coincidentally, these government-created “ghettos” began to be viewed as problematic by the government itself. So, a shift was made from public housing to privately owned rental housing,

also known as “Section 8.” This program allows lower-class families to rent privately owned housing. However, discrimination is still present within this housing system today (Letiecq et al.,2023). As previously mentioned, the housing system is not the only system the United States has implemented that is affected by structural racism. Our criminal justice system has succumbed to structural racism as well.

Structural racism has become especially “effective” through mass incarceration and the “War on Drugs.” People of color have been racially discriminated against for as far back as we can remember. Even when enslaved people became “free people,” a loophole was created within the 13th Amendment. As previously mentioned, the 13th Amendment made slavery illegal unless it was a form of punishment for crime, and coincidentally, the same year this amendment was created, the “Black Codes” were also made. These “Black Codes” were a series of laws designed to work against people of color in hopes of imprisoning them once again, but this time under legal laws (Goodman, 1912). These codes required all "Blacks and Mulattos" over the age of 18 to have written proof of employment. If they failed to, they would be convicted and imprisoned (Alexander, 2010). This would be the beginning of the mass incarceration system as we know it.

However, it did not hit its "peak" until the 1970s when the "War on Drugs" was declared by President Nixon due to the outbreak of drugs that were directly affecting the neighborhoods of the United States. It became particularly bad in the neighborhoods of New York City. The Nixon Administration even declared the minimum sentence for the possession of marijuana to be ten years in prison (Hawdon et al., 2022), which makes it all the more clear that imprisoning people of color was their ultimate goal. This "war," as John Erlichment would admit years after he departed from The White House Counsel, specifically targeted people of color and hippies directly with the criminalization of marijuana and cocaine. "We could arrest their leaders. raid

their homes, break up their meetings, and vilify them night after night on the evening news. Did we know we were lying about the drugs? Of course, we did" (Lobianco, 2016).

The "War on Drugs" that Nixon declared turned this rhetorical war into a real war. The "War on Drugs" was declared by Ronald Reagan in 1982. During his presidency, Reagan focused on criminalizing those who used drugs and throwing them behind bars rather than focusing on treatment and getting them help. Reagan even had the help of his wife, Nancy Reagan, with her "Just Say No" campaign, which was created to encourage the youth to say no to drugs in an attempt to prevent drug usage. It was during Reagan's presidency that crack cocaine evolved and began taking over impoverished streets. He took immediate action and established penalties for the possession and usage of crack. These penalties happened to be a lot harsher than those for powder cocaine, and as crack grew more popular within Black neighborhoods, this meant more Black bodies would be arrested and incarcerated in prisons. Similar to how Nixon had Ehrlichman, Reagan also had Lee Atwater. Atwater was Reagan's campaign strategist who was caught on tape in 1981 explaining the Southern Strategy.

Atwater said, "You start out in 1954 by saying 'N****r, N****r, N****r.' By 1964, you can't say 'N****r' anymore. That hurts you. It backfires. So you say stuff like forced bussing, state's rights, and all that stuff. You're getting so abstract now. You're talking about cutting taxes, and all of these things you're talking about are totally economic things, and the by-product of them is Blacks get hurt worse than whites." Atwater not only admits to the deliberate and purposeful racist actions that took place during the Reagan era, but he also admits that they were careful with their words to cover up the true injustice that they allowed and wanted to take place. However, the tactics used in both Nixon's and Reagan's presidencies were successful. By the

year 2000, there were a total of 1.1 million people added to the prison system, and 1 in 3 Black males were under police supervision (Bobo & Thompson, 2006).

These are only a few examples of institutions that run off of structural racism with the intent of bringing people of color down. As a result, the Black community was forced to search for ways to unite to cope during these times, and social justice groups emerged. Groups like these included the infamous Black Panther Party. The Black Panther Party was initially created to patrol and protect Black neighborhoods from police brutality. However, they quickly gained popularity amongst Black communities around the United States, and in response, they created a 10-point program. This 10-point program established its stand for self-defense in the Black community by fighting for issues such as freedom and an end to brutality against Blacks. Many found the Black Panthers unfavorable, which caused multiple violent outbreaks to erupt against the Panthers (Blackpast, 2018). Many of these cases involved police officers, as fighting police brutality against Blacks was one of their main concerns. Although violence was something the Panthers hoped to bring an end to, if they were met with it, they often had no choice but to resort to it. The violent instances that did involve the Panthers would be the drive the government would use to bring an end to the Panthers once and for all. To do so, the government coined The Black Panther Party “One of the greatest threats to the nation’s internal security” (Chang, 2005). Thus, COINELPRO was created to fight against communist groups in the United States. It was a national operation against Black nationalists, including the Nation of Islam and the Black Panthers. The FBI even worked with local police stations to arrest 348 Panthers (Chang, 2005). The Black Panthers ultimately did not stand a chance against the United States government, as a majority of its members were either imprisoned or killed. By 1982, the party was no longer together (History.com Editors, 2017), leaving the Black community to fight for themselves.

In “Keepin' It Real in Hip Hop Politics: A Political Perspective of Tupac Shakur,” Karin Stanford states that even Tupac Shakur was intensely involved in political groups at a young age. His parents had a prominent influence on this, as both his mother and stepfather were members of the Black Panther Party. He participated in the New Afrikan People’s Organization and eventually became the chair, where he would speak out and teach the youth. Shakur’s time with NAPO did not last long as he signed with his first record label soon after, where he would use his music as his platform for speaking out. Forming groups to unify and fight for the rights of their people was common in the Black community. It was a way for them to join and stick up for their community. Hip-hop and rap groups emerged from the same roots as activist groups. They collaborated to create beats and discuss topics affecting them and their community.

However, when social justice groups disappeared, the coping mechanism that gained popularity for many individuals within the Black community was drug usage. The effects of structural racism within these institutions can affect one's mental health significantly. A study done by the National Library of Medicine found that the initial motivator for drug usage/addiction is escapism (Jouhki & Oksanen, 2021). Merriam-Webster defines escapism as wanting to distract yourself from an unpleasant reality in any way, shape, or form. This means that the consumption of drugs was an outlet of escapism for many of the Black community, as the reality they were living in was constantly attempting to bring them down, whether it be police officers stopping them as they walked down the street or the government institutions denying them of help.

However, drug usage did not grow only as a coping mechanism. Drugs traveled through these neighborhoods so quickly because the act of selling them grew to be an efficient and easy way for fast cash. In *Black Noise*, Tricia Rose mentions the lack of job opportunities for the

Black community. She claims that the reason drug dealing grew to be popular in Black neighborhoods is because of the lack of job opportunities available to them, possibly caused by a lack of education or being turned away due to reasons involving race (Rose, 1994). In “Hip-Hop Wars: What We Talk About When We Talk About Hip-Hop,” Rose also argues that the loss of affordable housing, drug trade expansion, and the government's choice to incarcerate rather than rehabilitate these offenders are the key reasons why hip-hop mentions the topics that it does. All of which bring about a lack of opportunity within the Black community. Whether it be a lack of opportunity when it comes to what jobs they have access to, a lack of opportunity when it comes to affordable housing, and a lack of opportunity when it comes to what they will be allowed/not allowed to partake in or do following their release from prison, all in all, the Black community was being left out of specific opportunities, which gave them a significant disadvantage in surviving in the U.S. Thus, leading many of them to turn to music making and hip-hop because it was one of the few things they were able to access.

A study by National Development and Research Institutes, Inc. states that the crack epidemic caused many to fall victim to the usage of crack within poor neighborhoods. As a direct result, many families have been affected. The same study also states that even though crack began to grow out of popularity among the youth from 1998-1999, that of the 100,000 residents in Central Harlem were still using crack. This allows us to see the everlasting effects of a drug addiction like this. It has also been proven that involvement in incarceration, violence, and even the foster care system can raise the chances of one developing mental health issues (Vance, 2019). Major Depressive Disorder can even be passed down through genetics (Levinson & Nichols, n.d.). So, it may be possible that even the grandchildren of the Panther Party may suffer from depression as a direct result of the prejudice they faced in the 1970s. Resulting from these

mental health diseases, as mentioned previously, are issues like drug abuse and suicide. Studies show that from the year 1990-2003, there was a total of 28,177 suicides in the Black community. This is an increase of 2.1% (Molock & Crosby, 2006). The direct effects of imprisonment and mental health specifically are significantly reflected in the case of Kalief Browder.

In 2009, Browder was stopped by police officers walking home from a party in the Bronx. Browder was arrested and detained for a petty crime he did not commit. He was given a \$10,000 bail that he and his family could not afford, and Browder also denied the plea deal, finding it unethical to plead guilty when he did not commit the crime of stealing a backpack. Browder's denial of the plea deal resulted in him staying three years on Riker's Island in the Bronx, and 2 of those years were spent in solitary confinement. Incarceration activist and educator Liza Jessie Peterson argues that Browder was sent to solitary confinement and Riker's Island as a punishment for denying a plea deal and "challenging" the court system (Ava Duvernay & Jason Moran, 2016, 13TH. USA). Eventually, Browder was released from prison; however, two years following his release, Browder hung himself in his home in the Bronx. Browder's suicide is just one example of the effects that the incarceration system and structural racism may have on a member of the Black community. His death also serves as an example of how structural racism is causing great distress to the Black community and has been since the beginning.

All of these issues combined have forced the Black community to search for a sense of "escape" from reality through drug usage. A study done by the National Library of Medicine found that the initial motivator for drug usage/ addiction is escapism (Jouhki & Oksanen, 2021). Escapism can be best understood as wanting to distract yourself from the unpleasant reality in any way, shape, or form. This means that the consumption of drugs was an outlet of escapism for

many of the Black community, as the reality they were living in was constantly attempting to bring them down, whether it be police officers stopping them as they walked down the street or the government institutions denying them of help. A study found that between 1990-1998, Black males and females had the highest rates of deaths caused by overdose in New York City (Coffin et al., 2003). This corresponds to the Black community's hardships during this period, thus resulting in proof of a need and desire for escapism.

The Black community was dealing with the loss of their leaders and social justice groups. They were continuously being targeted by major government institutions, causing them to search for other outlets of escapism and self-expression.

During the summer of 1989, just one year after N.W.A released their controversial track, "F*** the Police," the hip-hop group was told they were not allowed to perform the song by the Detroit Police Department. Despite the police officer's request and a letter from the government requesting they not perform the song, the group insists and begins playing the song. Just 30 seconds into the track, the police release a cluster of gunshots, causing havoc, and N.W.A. is met backstage and thrown on the floor by a line of officers. Although the group was not arrested, they received a fine (Hughes, A. 2017. *The Defiant Ones*. HBO).

This track, "F**** the Police," represents what the Black community found in hip-hop. They were able to find an outlet of self-expression that allowed them to "fantasize" about taking their power back from those who oppressed them, like police officers, because doing so in real life could lead to violence or even death. Hip-hop became a sense of activism in the Black community because activist groups and individuals no longer existed as a result of oppression and violence. Due to the violence and murders that took place amongst social justice groups, members of the Black community may have steered away from participating or beginning social

justice groups similar to the Panthers. Coincidentally, the uprising of hip-hop took place simultaneously with the “War on Drugs” and the beginning of the mass incarceration system. Thus, hip-hop gave the Black community a way of self-expression that did not result in life-threatening events. This is why many young Black people turned to music-making in the ‘80s and '90s to replace the social justice groups and leaders that were taken away from the Black community.

Direct references to the era’s political situations also led to many hit records. In 1993, The Geto Boys released a track similar to the controversial N.W.A. hit. Sparking conversation regarding police brutality against the Black community once more, just two years after the beating of Rodney King. Proof of the social impact of structural racism is prominent in their song, “Crooked Officer.” The second verse goes as:

*“Oh, Mr. Officer, crooked officer, what’s happenin’?
You beat another Black man’s a**, and now you’re high cappin’
Friend, do I have to move to River Oaks
And bleach my f**** skin so I can look like these white folks?
Just to get some assistance
Because the brutality in my neighborhood is gettin’ persistent
’Cause you wanna harass me
Yeah, and if I talk back, you wanna bust my Black a**, G
Just like Rodney King
But if you try that shit with me, it’s gonna be a different scene”*

In this verse, the Geto Boys call out police officers for their discrimination against Blacks, specifically in their likeliness to act violently with members of the Black community. Being from Houston, Texas, they question whether or not they have to move to the suburbs of Houston and bleach their skin white to receive government assistance. They are referring to the social injustice within government programs and referencing Rodney King, who was mentioned previously. The anger caused by this event is reflected directly in the following line, suggesting that the encounter will end differently if officers approach them similarly.

Famous Rapper and activist Tupac Shakur was famously known for using his outlet as a music artist to speak out about racial justice issues time after time. Born and raised in Harlem, New York, Shakur had personal experiences with structural racism within programs and the emotional impact of it, which is prominent in the song “Who Do You Believe In?” The first verse goes:

*“I asked my homie on the block why he strapped, he laughed
Pointed his pistol as the cop car passed and blast
It's just another murder, nobody mourns no more
My tear drops gettin' bigger, but can't figure out what I'm cryin' for
Is it the miniature caskets, little babies
Victims of a stray from drug dealers gone crazy
Maybe it's just the drugs, visions of how the block was
Crack came, and it was strange how it rocked us
Perhaps the underlying fact stay high explains genocide
It's when we ride on our own kind”*

This snippet starts with Shakur's fellow gang member telling him that the reason for his weapon carrying is the police officers, and this is followed by Shakur stating that cop murders of Black people are so common that they are not mourned anymore. The emotional effect of these issues can be seen in the following line. Shakur emphasized the issue by stating that even babies are losing their lives and falling victim to police brutality. Reminiscent of the effects of the "War on Drugs" is also represented in this song as he mentions the homelessness caused by drug addiction that many view as an "easy way out." The following line goes, "*Crack came, and it was strange how it rocked us,*" which is a direct reference to the popularity of crack amongst the Black community as it was a cheaper option in the streets for cocaine. Lastly, Shakur suggests that the "War on Drugs" was a tactic used by the government to perform genocide against Black people and states that it is the racial discrimination against them that forces them to unite with each other. The Geto Boys highlight oppression's mental impact on the Black community in the "Mind Playing Tricks on Me" song released in 1991. On this track, The Geto Boys talk about the unnecessary paranoia that they experience as members of the Black community, which is a direct result of oppression and racial discrimination. They touch on feelings of someone being out to get them, but also about feeling suicidal at times due to the unprecedented paranoia they face on an everyday basis. Female hip-hop artists, too, mentioned the social and emotional impact of oppression in their songs. MC Lyte did so in her 1989 record, "Cappucino." In this song, MC Lyte paints a picture of being caught in the crossfire of a shoot-out, which causes her to lose her life for a split second. After regaining consciousness, Lyte expresses her gratitude for having her life spared. However, at the same time, she takes a second to question whether or not the afterlife was a better option, as she did not have to worry about stray bullets, murderers, or gang members.

The Black community was significantly affected both socially and emotionally by structural racism in the United States. Being confined to a living space that is filled with impoverished people with a lack of resources, in combination with easy access to drugs, can affect one's mental health significantly. As hip-hop artists and members of the Black community of the 1980s-1990s witnessed these issues firsthand, their music now acts as storybooks that describe the hardships they faced in their everyday lives.

Most hip-hop artists' upbringing included firsthand experiences with the War on Drugs and the mass incarceration system, a reflection of it is also prominent in the music. From early groups like Grandmaster Flash and the Furious Five to the infamous Too Short, many of them left proof of their experiences and hardships within their records. Female rapper Remy Ma spoke about her memories growing up in the Bronx during the crack epidemic in the Netflix Documentary "*Ladies First*." Ma said, "Seeing people, you know, nodding off in the corner. I didn't even know why. I remember seeing so many crack vials just everywhere. We used to call them sprinkles. We used to literally collect them in different colors... I was too young to understand" (Twigg, 2020). Through Remy Ma's experience as a young child, we can see how drug usage became normalized within poor communities, so much so that drug paraphernalia became common enough to act as children's toys.

The "War on Drugs" nationwide impact extended to the Bay Area of California, where artist Too Short also dealt with it firsthand, which he speaks about in his song "The Ghetto." The second verse states:

"Cause to me, life is one hard rap

Even though my sister smoked crack cocaine

She was nine months pregnant, ain't nothing changed

*600 million on a football team
And her baby died just like a dope fiend
The story I tell is so incomplete
Five kids in the house, no food to eat
Don't look at me, and don't ask me why
Mama's next door getting high
Even though she's got five mouths to feed
She'd rather spend her money on a H-I-T"*

Through this song, Too Short is speaking about his own family situation and his experience growing up with a family that was heavily affected by drug addiction as a young Black American. Too Short compares life in “the ghetto” to a hard rap, using the phrase as a double meaning to set the stage for the hardships and obstacles he has overcome. At the same time, he also emphasizes his skill as an artist in creating these lines or raps. He also mentions the drug usage cycle his mother is stuck in and the generational pattern of substance abuse as his sister is also stuck in the same cycle even despite her being pregnant. Too Short even discusses how his mother chooses to spend her cash on drugs rather than using it to feed and care for the many children she has. This was a reality for many Black Americans, especially those from Los Angeles, like Too Short.

Hip-hop groups have touched on the topic of substance abuse and illegal drug dealing since the beginning of hip-hop. Grandmaster Flash and the Furious Five did so on their “White Lines” record, released in 1983. Just four years later, N.W.A. also made a hit about this subject in the record “Dopeman.” The effect that drugs have on the Black community as a direct result of

the 'War on Drugs' has continued to bleed into hip-hop since the beginning of hip-hop because many of these artists are members of the Black community.

Many rappers also spoke about being arrested and imprisoned in their records. Public Enemy was notoriously known for speaking out against the government and fighting for the rights of Blacks. This is explicitly heard in the record "Black Steel in the Hour of Chaos." The second verse goes,

*"They got me rotting in the time that I'm serving
Telling you what happened the same time they're throwing
Four of us packed in a cell like slaves, oh well*

The same motherfucker got us living in his hell

*You have to realize, what is a form of slavery
Organized under a swarm of devils
Straight up - word 'em up on the level*

The reasons are several, most of them federal"

Chuck D outwardly makes the connection between the imprisonment system and slavery. Many rappers mentioned issues of the prison system, but they went unnoticed. Hip-hop became a signal that drew attention to the crisis among the Black youth (Chang, 2005).

Mass incarceration and the “War on Drugs” heavily influenced this era of Hip-Hop by providing a tool for the Black community to fight against the oppression they faced. Public Enemy was not the only hip-hop group using their songs to speak about their experiences with the prison system. Tupac graphically recalls what takes place within the confines of a prison cell in his 1997 record “16 on Death Row,” similar to Nas, who also mentions his experiences within the confines of a prison cell in his record “Last Words” from 1999. Other socially powerful topics were also often discussed in these songs.

Hip-hop artists often used their music to direct attention towards movements and pay tribute to past leaders. Hip-hop artist Paris released music regarding Black power. This is especially prominent in the song “Panther Power.” The third verse goes as,

“Black and strong and not down to half-step

Piece is kept, police are ripped

P do not plea, it's a new direction

Strength and unity, peace, protection

One for Huey, and the movement won't die

And the strong survive, the panther power”

In this, Paris speaks about the Black Panther Party specifically and touches on what it would have been like if peace had been accomplished between whites and Blacks while the Panther Party was active. He mentions what the Panthers stood for and even pays respect to the Panther's founder, Huey P. Newton. This song can be viewed as a dedication to the Panthers for their sacrifices for the Black community. Through this, it becomes clear that hip-hop became an outlet of self-expression that the youth would run to as it was a safer option. Social Justice

became a running theme in hip-hop at this time. Dr. Dre also uses music as his outlet to express his emotions and hardships. In the documentary “*The Defiant Ones*,” Dr. Dre says it can be impossible to recover from certain things, such as the death of a loved one, so he has turned to music to get through it. “You just figure out ways to deal with it because there are still people here that need me, so I gotta pick my sh** up and suck it up and get active. I turn to music as an outlet to have a place to go, like the studio, to be creative. ...It helps get your mind out of the dark areas,” Dre said, “That's my way of coping with it” (Hughes, A. 2017. *The Defiant Ones*. HBO)..

Music and hip-hop became the back communities' way of speaking on topics that mattered to them and became a safe space for a cry for help among the drug-infested streets of the United States. With hip-hop, everyday people were able to talk about issues like drugs, abuse, and the death of their loved ones without fear of losing their own lives. The mark of this era is embedded into early hip-hop as countless songs remain cries for help from the Black community. Boogie Down Productions' “Stop the Violence” portrays just that. The lyrics go as,

“Some wish to destroy this scene called hip-hop

But I won't drop

Not I or Scott LaRock

Now, here is the message that we bring today:

Hip-hop will surely decay

If we as a people don't stand up and say:

‘Stop the violence!’”

Hip-hop artist and co-founder of the “Stop the Violence Movement,” KRS-One, mentions many wish for hip-hop to be destroyed, but he and Scott LaRock, his co-founder of Boogie Down Productions, will not allow it. KRS-One created the “Stop the Violence Movement” to unite hip-hop artists and encourage and end violence within hip-hop. He created this movement just after the unfortunate murder of Scott LaRock due to his death taking place as a result of street violence (Coe, 2018). His main goal in this movement was to end street violence among the Black community and the youth. The movement included Dwayne Sumal, D-Nice, Kenny Parker, Lee Smith, Levi 167, Ms. Melodie, Pamela Scott, Red Alert, Sidney Mills, and KRS-One (Bradley & Dubios, 2011). In a 1988 UK TV interview, KRS-one described the reasoning for forming BPD and how he hoped to bring a change to the streets of New York. “BDP was basically designed for two full purposes,” KRS-One said, “One was to grasp that street image, that street life we lived, and to put it in a mainstream sense because the ghetto has no one to speak to them.” As KRS’s words demonstrate, “Stop the Violence” was a direct way for the hip-hop community to address people’s desires for hip-hop to disappear by contextualizing the topics discussed in hip-hop songs. As the STV movement hit the East Coast, “The West Coast Rap Allstars” were forming across the U.S. also to bring an end to gang violence amongst the Black youth. In 1990, they released the “We’re all in the Same Gang” track to work towards that. This “Allstar” group consisted of Eazy-E, Dr. Dre, MC Ren, Digital Underground, Ice-T, MC Hammer, Michel’le, Tone-Lōc, King Tee, Above the Law, J.J. Fad, Young MC, Body & Soul, Oaktowns 3.5.7, and Def Jef, who all came together to encourage peace amongst the streets of L.A. (Williams, 2022). Thus, hip-hop artists worldwide used hip-hop to unite the Black community in many ways. Even female hip-hop artists were known for doing this. Queen Latifah released the hit record “U.N.I.T.Y.” in 1993, where she touches on the lack of respect men have

for women around this time and specifically talks about domestic violence issues as well as harassment that women experience on the streets. Therefore, it is evident that uniting with one another is a recurring theme in hip-hop. Individuals not affected by these issues had the privilege to turn the other cheek and judge hip-hop and rappers based on their language and issues. However, these unfavorable topics, such as drugs, alcohol, and violence, were only being discussed due to their familiarity with them amongst Black communities that was caused and supported by United States laws. This song proves that hip-hop artists used their voices to bring awareness to discriminatory issues during this time as a form of escapism and an opportunity to make the public aware of the daily experiences people of color undergo.

Thus, when an individual describes hip-hop as “violence encouraging loud noise,” they are dismissing all of the oppression the Black community has faced. From slavery to contemporary mass incarceration and being viewed as ideal targets for the “War on Drugs” as well as police officers and government officials, it is all thrown onto the back burner when a claim like that is made.

As government laws have improved in the treatment of the Black community, the scars are still there and all the more visible when we look back at early hip-hop and rap. Although this paper just scratches the surface, it is made clear that the genre of hip-hop stemmed from the oppression the Black community was faced with in the 1970s-1990s. Throughout this paper, I have primarily focused on songs from this period that reflect the hardships faced. Due to the heightened “War on Drugs,” the new mass incarceration system, and other U.S. institutions that demonstrate structural racism, members of the Black community were drawn to hip-hop as it allowed them the opportunity to speak their minds freely while maintaining their safety unlike joining social justice groups, which would often lead to violent outbreaks with authoritative

figures and result in the murder of police officers and fellow social justice group members, or often feeding the mass incarceration system.

Evidence of the impact caused by oppression against the Black community is prominent in hip-hop of the 80s and 90s, and this is what outsiders view as “unnecessary promotion of violence.” These songs mention these unfavorable topics because they are the artist's everyday experiences. It reflects the oppression that bleeds into our systems, such as housing and employment, which results in social impacts, such as being confined to poverty-stricken neighborhoods, and emotional impacts, like the development of depression or anxiety disorders. These songs serve as recorded records of evidence proving the effects that the severe forms of oppression the Black community underwent were cruel enough to have a lasting impact on one's mental health and social well-being. However, when an entire nation seemed to be working against them, hip-hop artists made it their mission to remind the Black community to remain strong and unite.

In today's mainstream hip-hop music, unity and a push towards political power is often lacking. While some artists continue embedding political themes in their work, in the same way that these artists did many decades ago, they are considered underground and found on platforms like Soundcloud and YouTube. These platforms do not allow them to gain as much revenue or publicity as popular commercial artists focusing on gang life's flashy elements. Modern-day artists like Vince Staples and Kendrick Lamar have discussed social justice and equality within their songs. Still, it is not done as often and to the extent that Public Enemy and other hip-hop artists did during the era of the “War on Drugs.” After all, when YG attempted to make his own political statement, he was essentially hushed. Nevertheless, he did not allow the track to be removed from streaming platforms or stop performing it live; instead, he used it as fuel to keep

the song alive. YG's actions demonstrate why it is our responsibility as a society to encourage artists to create songs that hold political power, and when they do create them, we must show our utmost respect for them. These songs hold more power than one would think and can spark conversation and change.

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